

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXI. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with Chelating Azo Dye Ligands 1-(2'-Hydroxynaphthyl-1')-azo-2-hydroxybenzene, 1-(Acetylacetyl-3')-azo-2-hydroxybenzene, 3-(3'-Acetoacetanilido)azo-1-hydroxybenzene and 3-(8'-Hydroxyquinonyl-5')-azo-1-hydroxybenzene

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Bis-bidentate title ligands having ONNO, ONOO and ONON potential donor atoms form polymeric complexes with divalent metal ions. As inferred from analysis, conductance, magnetic, ir, electronic and esr spectral data, the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are six-coordinated with an octahedral or distorted-octahedral configuration and the Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are four-coordinated with a tetrahedral geometry around the metal ions.

AZO dyes exhibit strong pharmacological activities¹ and are used for dyeing food stuff and preserving food grains². These are also used in potentiometric and spectrophotometric analyses³ and as versatile chelating ligands⁴. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise new multidentate chelating azo dyes possessing ONNO, ONOO and ONON donor atoms and their di- and polymeric metal complexes with divalent cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, cadmium and mercury ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. make. The ligands were prepared by the coupling reaction of diazonium chlorides obtained from *m*-aminophenol with the alkaline solution of β -naphthol, acetylacetone, acetoacetanilide and 8-hydroxyquinoline respectively.

Preparation of complexes: The metal complexes were prepared by adding ethanolic solutions of the metal chlorides separately to the ligands dissolved in dioxane in 1 : 1 molar ratio. On raising pH of the solution to around 7 the metal complexes separated out, then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal and nitrogen contents were estimated by standard procedures. Conductance measurements of the complexes were made in DMF solutions (10^{-3} M). The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398

spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M in DMF) on a Hilger and Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-4 spectrometer at room temperature.

Analytical and physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show the formation of 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes with the composition $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, $[\text{M}'_2\text{L}_2]$, $[\text{ML}'/\text{L}''/\text{L}'''.2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ $[\text{ML}'/\text{L}''/\text{L}''']_n$, where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $\text{M}' = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $\text{LH}_2 = 1$ -(2'-hydroxynaphthyl-1')-azo-2-hydroxybenzene; $\text{L}'\text{H}_2 = 1$ -(acetylacetyl-3')-azo-2-hydroxybenzene; $\text{L}''\text{H}_2 = 3$ -(3'-acetoacetanilido)-azo-1-hydroxybenzene; $\text{L}'''\text{H}_2 = 3$ -(8'-hydroxyquinonyl-5')-azo-1-hydroxybenzene (Table 1). The complexes are stable at room temperature even upto 120° indicating coordination of the water molecules. They are amorphous in nature having high melting points, and insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. The complexes are found to be non-electrolytic in nature having molar conductance in the range 4.7–8.1 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$.

In the ir spectra of the azo dye ligands, the band observed at $\sim 3400 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (OH), was lowered due to intramolecular O–H...O and O–H...N hydrogen bonding⁵. In the metal complexes this band disappeared indicating deprotonation of OH showing the coordination of both the phenolic and enolic oxygen atoms to the metal atom. In the ligands,

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % :		μ_{eff} B.M.	Mol. wt.
		Found	(Calcd.)		
		M	N		
LH ₂	Red	—	10.20 (10.61)	—	225
L'H ₂	Red	—	12.30 (12.73)	—	205
L''H ₂	Orange red	—	13.80 (14.14)	—	262
L'''H ₂	Red	—	13.50 (13.85)	—	248
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	16.10 (16.50)	7.60 (7.84)	2.8	640
[Ni ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Light brown	16.10 (16.46)	7.30 (7.85)	2.6	680
[Cu ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Green	17.20 (17.57)	7.40 (7.74)	1.4	650
[Zn ₂ L ₂ (H ₂)]	Buff	19.30 (19.98)	8.20 (8.56)	—	610
[Cd ₂ L ₂]	Light yellow	29.60 (30.02)	7.20 (7.48)	—	690
[Hg ₂ L ₂]	Grey	43.10 (43.36)	5.80 (6.05)	—	850
[CoL'(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Brown	18.50 (18.82)	8.40 (8.95)	5.1	285
[NiL'(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Black	18.30 (18.77)	8.60 (8.95)	3.2	270
[CuL'(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Brown	19.40 (20.00)	8.10 (8.82)	1.8	280
[ZnL'] _n	Reddish brown	22.40 (23.08)	9.4 (9.88)	—	265
[CdL'] _n	Light brown	33.50 (34.02)	8.30 (8.47)	—	290
[HgL'] _n	Grey	47.60 (47.92)	6.20 (6.69)	—	370
[CoL''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Reddish brown	14.70 (15.11)	10.20 (10.77)	5.1	375
[NiL''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Brown	14.80 (15.06)	11.20 (11.74)	3.3	367
[CuL''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Green	15.90 (16.10)	10.20 (10.65)	1.8	378
[ZnL''] _n	Brownish grey	17.80 (18.15)	11.20 (11.65)	—	347
[CdL''] _n	Yellowish brown	27.20 (27.59)	9.80 (10.31)	—	387
[HgL''] _n	Red	42.80 (43.27)	8.80 (9.06)	—	457
[CoL'''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Orange	16.20 (16.46)	11.20 (11.74)	5.0	332
[NiL'''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Brown	16.10 (16.41)	11.40 (11.74)	3.2	345
[CuL'''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	Pink	17.20 (17.52)	11.20 (11.65)	1.7	344
[ZnL'''] _n	Brown	18.70 (19.91)	12.30 (12.79)	—	318
[HgL'''] _n	Red	42.80 (43.27)	8.80 (9.06)	—	435

the bands at 1 510 (LH₂), 1 520 (L'H₂), 1 520 (L''H₂) and 1 515 cm⁻¹ (L'''H₂) can be assigned to phenolic C—O vibration and its shifting by 5–15 cm⁻¹ in the metal chelates indicates the coordination of phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal atom. The bands at 1 595 (LH₂), 1 605 (L'H₂), 1 620 (L''H₂) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (L'''H₂) may be assigned to —N=N— vibrations. A lowering of this band around 150 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes with the ligand (LH₂) indicates the coordination of both the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal atoms and by 25–70 cm⁻¹ with the latter ligands show the bonding with one of the azo nitrogen atoms⁶. The ligands L'H₂ and L''H₂

can exist in two tautomeric keto and enol forms. Three bands at ~1 670 (C=C), ~1 605 (C=O) and ~1 170 cm⁻¹ (C—O) have been observed in the ligands. These frequencies showed negative shifts in the spectra of the metal complexes indicating the bonding of amide carbonyl oxygen and acetyl carbonyl oxygen atoms to the metal atoms⁷. In the spectra of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, the presence of coordinated water molecules is indicated by the appearance of a broad band at 3 050–3 400 cm⁻¹ followed by a sharp peak at 845 cm⁻¹ assigned to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively⁸.

Sub-normal magnetic moments of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with the ligand LH₂ are indicative of the presence of π -type antiferromagnetic and ferromagnetic exchange interaction respectively, between the metal atoms in a dimetallic structure. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with the rest of the ligands exhibited normal magnetic moments expected for high-spin octahedral complexes⁹.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes exhibit four band at ~8 520, ~17 155, ~19 850 and ~32 000 cm⁻¹, the last band being a CT band and the first three bands may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), →⁴A_{2g}(F) and →⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively in conformity with an octahedral configuration. The spectral parameters *Dq*, *B*, β , ν_2/ν_1 and σ (Table 2) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the Co^{II} complexes¹⁰. In case of the Ni^{II} complexes, four bands appear at ~11 050, ~16 270, ~22 850 and ~30 600 cm⁻¹. The first three bands are attributed to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), →³T_{1g}(F) (ν_2) and →³T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) transitions and the last band to a CT band¹¹. Distorted octahedral geometry is suggested to the Cu^{II} complexes with a broad band at ~13 360–15 560 cm⁻¹ with the maxima at ~14 350 cm⁻¹ assignable to ²E_g→²T_{2g} transition¹².

 TABLE 2—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF Co^{II} AND Ni^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	<i>Dq</i> cm ⁻¹	<i>B</i> cm ⁻¹	β	ν_2/ν_1	σ
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	852	563	0.579	2.01	74.4
[CoL'(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	847	803	0.827	2.02	20.9
[CoL''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	916	847	0.814	2.02	22.8
[CoL'''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	920	848	0.815	2.03	22.7
[Ni ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	522	665	0.539	1.47	56.4
[NiL'(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	518	668	0.642	1.47	59.9
[NiL''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	1 130	607	0.625	1.60	60.0
[NiL'''(H ₂ O) ₂] _n	1 135	605	0.625	1.60	60.32

The esr spectra of two polycrystalline copper(II) complexes at Q-band have been recorded. In case of complex [CuL''(H₂O)₂]_n, the spectrum indicates that the hyperfine lines of Cu^{II} are well-resolved indicating that the dipolar and exchange interaction between Cu^{II} ions are negligible. This in turn indicates that the Cu^{II}—Cu^{II} distance is sufficiently large due the bulky ligands. The value of *g* for the complex comes out to be 2.016 with *A* value of 76 gauss. The esr spectrum of the complex [CuL'''

$(H_2O)_2]_n$ is isotropic consisting of a single line with a g -value of 2.3, characteristic of regular octahedral symmetry. This type of spectrum may result either due to grossly misaligned tetragonal axes which may

be reducing the symmetry or due to the fact that a regular octahedral stereochemistry undergoing a dynamic or pseudo-rotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or a chromophore of symmetry lower than octahedral may undergo free rotation¹³.

Considering the bis-bidentate nature of the ligands the probable structure (LH_2) of the complexes can be represented by structure 1, where both the benzene rings are in *cis*-position or by 2, where both the benzene rings are in *trans*-position. The latter geometry is more preferred from steric consideration. Assuming the ligands $(L'H_2)$ and $(L''H_2)$ to be double-bidentate, this would indicate that both the water molecules in the formula unit $[ML'/L''.2H_2O]_n$ are coordinated to the metal. The two chain structures for $[ML'/L''.2H_2O]_n$ may be envisaged (3a) with metal having the same set of donor atoms MNO_3 and with alternate metal atoms having MN_2O_2 and MO_4 (plus water) ligand arrangements (3b). Similarly, the other ligands $(L''H_2)$, acting as double-bidentate forms octahedral complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , and one possible chain-polymer structure (4) can be suggested for these complexes with the same set of donor atoms MN_2O_2 . An analogous tetrahedral structure can be envisaged for the Zn, Cd and Hg complexes without the water molecules.

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